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Detection of Different Mechanical Forces by Multidirectional Sensors

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Acknowledgement

Prof. Chun Wang

Dr. Shuying Wu

Ms Fan Zhang

Ms Yuyan Yu

Mr Benjamin Xia

Prof. Nigel Lovell

ARC DECRA Fellowship

UNSW EMU

Background: Soft and stretchable sensors

Human-robot interface

Image source: Silicon Valley Innovation Center

Wearable human health monitoring

J. Mater. Chem. B, 2018, 6, 4043-4064

Current state: Multidirectional sensors

Single resistive sensor

Sensor array

Adv. Mater. Technol. 2017, 2, 1600188

ACS Nano, 2014, 8 (12), pp 12020–12029

Sci. Robot. 3, eaau6914 (2018)

Tension, compression and shearing

Design of multidirectional sensor

Fabrication process

Lateral tension

Normal pressure

Shearing

Detection of multiple forces

Summary

- Sugar as template to fabricate low-cost sensors;
- Asymmetric sandwiched structure;
- Highly stretchable, multidirectional, and good stability;
- Differentiation of tension, compression, and shearing.